

Fire Controlling Robo Car

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Abstract: The security of human life from sudden fire outbreaks at home, factory, office, building, and laboratory is very important. This paper presents a multi-sensor-based fire-controlling robo-car which intends to detect and fight against fire with the help of three flame sensors. If a fire breaks out in any area the fire-controlling robo-car uses its three flame sensors to find the source of the fire outbreak and move to that place to extinguish the fire. A Flame detector is more advantageous than a smoke detector as it puts off the fire as soon as it finds out without waiting for the object to burn. When a flame sensor detects smoke before or after the fire breaks, it pours water over the burning surface. The robo-car detects fire using the flame sensor without any human help. First, the robot detects the fire or smoke using the sensor and thereafter it moves to the spot and puts off the fire by pouring water. While doing so it maintains a proper distance from the fire and returns to its original place after the fire is extinguished.

Keywords–Microcontroller; flame; alarm; pump

1. Introduction

Robots in today's world are mainly used to reduce the pressure on humans as well as their efforts. Today robotics is the fastest-growing engineering field. Robots are mainly used to remove people from laborious and precarious work. In this paper, we present the idea of a Fire Controlling Robo Car. With the help of fire controlling robocar property damages and life, casualties can be saved from sudden outbreaks of fire. A Fire controlling robot is planned to detect the source of fire such as in houses or factories and then it would promptly put off the fire. The chief purpose is to make use of this robot in fire-prone areas and the robot will instantly start its work as soon as it detects the fire breakout. This robot assists will rescue operations during fire breakouts where the entry of the fireman is not easy. There are many types of vehicles for extinguishing fires at home, factories, etc. but we choose fire controlling robocar to control fire remotely. By using fire controlling robocar the spotting and rescue activity can be done in a guarded way without putting firemen in peril and precarious situation. Currently, the methods applied in firefighting is poor and ineffective and highly dependent on a human who is prone to make error regardless of how highly they have been trained. But nowadays the use of robots in firefighting has become popular as it is precarious for any person to involve themselves in such a situation. In our project, we are developing a robot which can find out and extinguish a fire at any point. Our robocar explores the surroundings and avoids any hindrance. The Arduino board act as the brain of the whole control circuit. It consists of three sensors that are linked to the control circuit. The Sensor is used to find out the fire breakout and moves the robocar to the location of the breakout. As soon as the robocar reaches the location the pump connected gets into functions and extinguishes the fire.

2. Methodology

The fire-controlling robocar presented in this paper intends to help the user to control any fire breakout. It uses a flame sensor for fire detection operation and is based on the microcontroller Arduino UNO which is the brain of the robocar circuit. The robocar is equipped with a water tank, a pipe for putting off the fire along with an inbuilt water pump.

At an initial stage, the flame sensor detects if there is any fire outbreak and thereafter estimates the outbreak location. It then deciphers the processed data to the receiver end and the receiver circuit now establishes communication with the Arduino. The Arduino then processes the instructions to direct and move the robocar to the desired location with the help of the motor. Arduino does this work via Bluetooth controller. The working range of the Bluetooth controller is 100 meters. Hence our robo-car is capable of working in the range of 100 meters. Arduino also simultaneously operates the water pump with the help of the motor driver and aims it in the desired direction henceforth instructing the water pump to pour water and extinguish the fire. If the flame or smoke is not within the range of the sensor then it changes its location and moves forward and rechecks the presence of flame or smoke within the new range. The robocar will start moving only after the sensor detects the source of smoke or fire within its range. This system allows a person to use the robocar and extinguish the fire by being at a risk-free distance from the fire breakouts.

A. Design

Fig 1. Block Diagram of the Fire Controlling Robo Car

B. Hardware Used

This fire-controlling robocar consists of three sensors, the main part of the robocar is Arduino UNO (microcontroller), which controls the other components used. Two motor drivers have been used to make the wheel which is connected by the DC motor and pump work. A pipe is mounted on the servo motor which draws water from the tank and helps to extinguish the fire.

1. Flame sensor: This sensor is mainly designed for locating as well as responding to the occurrence of a fire or smoke. It detects the fire with 3 flame sensors which are arranged in three directions; right, left and middle. The detection range is 760-1100nm. The preliminary work is to lessen the risk associated with combustion.
2. DC Motor: It is a type of electric motor that converts DC electrical power into mechanical power that a DC supply is converted to rotational movement. DC motor gives 500 RPM at 12V, motor runs smoothly from 4V to 12V and gives a vast range of RPM, and torque. This project is used to connect the wheel of the robocar.
3. Driver Module: Here two motor drivers have been used; L298N and L293.
 - i) L298N: It is a two-H-Bridge motor driver. It controls the direction and speed of two DC motors. This is based on the voltage used at the VCC. If in case the supply voltage is up to 12V then we can enable the 5V regulator and the 5V pin can be used as output.
 - ii) L293: L293 motor driver is a quadruple high current half-H driver. It provides bidirectional drive currents up to 1A at voltages from 4.5V to 36V. Inductive loads like relays, solenoids, DC and bipolar stepping motors, as well as other high current and high voltage loads, can be driven by these devices.
4. Servo motor: it consists of AC or DC motor, a potentiometer, a controlling circuit and a gear assembly. Servo SG90 has been used in this project. It can rotate up to 180 degrees. It works at 4.8 V to 6 V.
5. Submersible pump: By converting rotatory energy into kinetic energy and pressure energy, a submersible pump brings water to the surface. This is accomplished by drawing water into the pump where the water is pushed through the diffuser by the impeller's rotation.
6. Arduino UNO: It is a microcontroller board based on ATmega328P. It consists of 14 digital input-output pins and 6 Analog inputs. It works based on the program in Arduino IDE with the help of a type B USB cable.
7. Bluetooth controller: It is used for wireless communication. It is designed in such a way that it replaces the cable connection and uses serial communication to communicate with electronics.
8. Buzzer: It has been used to create an alarming sound as soon as it detects smoke or flame.
9. Water tank: It has been used to store water. 250ml small tank has been used in this project.

C. Software Used

Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment): It's a software used to write codes with

the help of a text editor. It connects with the Arduino hardware with the help of a type-B USB cable to upload the programs.

3. Result Analysis

An autonomous firefighting robot that can successfully detect and extinguish flames and smoke has been implemented in this project. This robot is perfectly able to move forward, left, and right direction. The robocar's movement is controlled by the Arduino code and the motors. In any situation, if there is any smoke or fire the flame sensors are activated, and a buzzer will start to sound. Upon receiving a signal about the danger of the environment, the motor will begin to rotate, move the car to the danger point, and begin pumping water with the assistance of a servo motor. This procedure will continue until the fire or smoke is completely put out. At the first test run the flame sensor was not working. On changing the flame sensor, we were able to test the working of the sensor. The simulation was run after the project was built successfully, and the desired result was obtained.

4. Conclusion

The Fire Controlling Robo Car can fight a fire on a small scale with enough power. It is better able to detect fire flames in dimly lit areas. Since it can distinguish fire in a flash and put it off before spreading. This robot has a sensor, like a smoke or flame sensor. A water spraying mechanism is activated to put out the fire if it is detected. Additionally, the operator is notified of all events via a sound alert. With sufficient funding and scope, this robot design can also fight large fires with more reserve capacity and a better sensing unit that can even detect fires earlier in all situations. In conclusion, the "Fire Controlling Robo Car" project has accomplished its goals.

The experimental robocar prototype could be transformed into a practical robocar as part of future work, which would necessitate enhancing the robot's overall performance. A face detection system can be implemented in our prototype so that it can detect the faces of any human or animal and create a signal and send it back to the person operating it. It will be beneficial for firefighters to save people who are trapped in a fire. The ultrasonic sensor can also be attached to prevent the robot from colliding with other objects. Its performance can also be improved by connecting it to a wireless zooming camera with a higher resolution so that the person controlling it can see how the robot is working from a distance on a screen.

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